

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

The Coin as a Parameter Hub:

FAIRified Data from the Die Study of Apollonia Pontica through Corpus Nummorum

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Dataship Concept

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Parameters Contained by a Coin

The controlled mass production of coins makes these objects suitable for standardized documentation. Numismatic studies often contain rich catalogs that compile a perfect source of data. They provide a wide range of chronological and geographical reference points as well as other fundamental data from the archaeological sciences. When enriched with its metadata the coin is an archaeological parameter hub for almost all kinds of other objects (**Table 1**). It is because they bear obvious historical evidence. A coin is a medium showing the characteristics of several types of monuments – epigraphic with their legends, iconographic, and stylistic with their imagery. Those can be controlled by an authority and influenced by local traditional motifs.

COIN	Legend/ Inscription	Iconography	Style	Metal composition	Size	Weight (standard)	Mint/ Workshop	Findspot Circulation	Context
Sculpture	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
Epigraphic monument	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
Seals, gems	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓
Vessels (ceramic & metal)	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Decorative objects				✓		✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1. An example of comparable parameters of coins and other objects

But there is more to the three very important characteristics that connect coins to unique media such as statues, reliefs, or inscriptions of any kind. It contains parameters usual for other archaeological objects, that is size, weight, metal composition, very importantly, archaeological context and circulation for geographical analyses. Having mass production in mind, large or even enormous quantities of objects and thus data emerge. That can otherwise be found only when studying fragmented objects, like pottery for instance. However, coins dispose of iconographic and text data like the rare media, which is needed to make image recognition work and create automated statistics and visualizations. This is the reason why numismatics excels in digital tools and semantic web linkage.

A single coin object can be attributed with some of the basic characteristics of numismatics only after being studied and evaluated as part of many. A typological or die study reveals new aspects of the artifact. Which ones, however, depends often on the research question and that is why the recycling of the coin data is needed.

The Data from the Die Study of Apollonia Pontica

Apollonia Pontica is a known mint, and its coinage is the ground basis for research on other coinages¹ and the fractured history in Thrace, the Black Sea Area, Northern Greece, and even Eastern Asia Minor. It serves both as the core evidence and a missing link.

The Dissertation "Die Münzprägung von Apollonia Pontike. Die Bildthemen einer griechischen Polis im pontisch-thrakischen Raum" contains 4525 coins. It not only added parameters to the coins such as dating or minting standards and denomination, but it produced by analyzing them iconographically and stylistically further entries with their metadata about the dies used, and the types they can be grouped in. The newly generated data comprises 465 obverse dies, 751 reverse dies, and 88 types in a hierarchic typology with subtypes and variants or in a flat typology with 235 types. The coin data comes from publications, excavation documentation, inventory books of private and institutional collections, including members of the NFDI4Objects consortium².

The catalog entry looks as follows:

Bronze

Großnominal: Oktochalkon

Typ 53 Apollonkopf nach r./Apollon letros

Variante 53.1 mit Magistrat ΚΑΛΛΙΣΤΡΑΤΟΥ

Vs.: Kopf des Apollon mit Lorbeerkrantz nach r.

Rs.: ↓ ΑΠΟΛΛΩΝΟΣ / ΙΗΤΡΟΥ // → ΚΑΛΛΙ-ΣΤΡΑΤΟΥ

Apollon stehend von vorn, Kopf nach links, in der Rechten Lorbeerzweig mit Raben, in der Linken Pfeil und Bogen haltend. Bildleiste.

3897. V418 – R675: 24,6–26,3 mm; 10,76 g; D 4,1 mm; 12 h; Rs. Gegenstempel Athenakopf mit Helm nach rechts. FO: Malkoto kale, Ravadinovo (arch. Stätte); Burgas, RAM, Inv. A900; Abb. H. Ivanova-Anaplioti

Thus, a coin dataset includes the following parameters: type, obverse die, reverse die, owner, inv. no., diameter min and max, thickness, weight, die axis, find spot, provenance, additional technical details (centerhole, counterstrike, double strike, pierced, etc.), photographer and copyright, and reference.

¹ For instance Histria, Thracian Chersonese, Parion and others that are all contained in common coin hoards and cover common circulation area.

² i. e. the Coin Cabinet of the Staatliche Museen zu Berlin and many University Collections in Germany.

A type, subtype, or variant dataset includes obverse and reverse description, obverse and reverse legends and their directions, period, phase, material, weight standard, and denomination.

A die dataset includes obverse or reverse description, obverse or reverse legend, and their direction. It is bound to the following parameters fostered by the type: period, phase, material, weight standard, and denomination.

All the data, including the newly created content, is safely stored in tables that were used for the export of the catalog and can be tidied and easily prepared to be published as a dataset. A major challenge in the life cycle of this research data is to publish it in a sustainable form that allows reuse, additions, and corrections. This is due to the growth in the amount of material, which is supplemented annually by new finds from excavations.

To store this data and reuse it properly it is crucial to enter it into an accessible database or portal. After proper attribution and addition of linked data, this object can then be compared with other coinages or even other material groups, by using common parameters as simple as the archeological context. There is a complex connection between the datasets because one die, being only an obverse one, can occur in two or more types, those characterized by the descriptions of both sides. That is why it is wiser to import the numismatic data in an already functioning portal with a data model and Linked Open Data (LOD) to ensure a full life cycle (Dierkes, 2021).

The Portal Corpus Nummorum

Thankfully there is such a portal to accommodate the numismatics of Thrace and interlink it – Corpus Nummorum (CN). It is a crucial research instrument because Thrace is an important linking region and has many research gaps: missing coin typologies of other mints, and iconographic misinterpretations. Also, fundamental historical gaps exist because of the fragmented literary sources. So, we depend on the interpretation of interconnected archaeological material. For this purpose, it is important to use a portal reaching the Maturity Level 4 (Devaraju et al., 2020; FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, 2020) of data as CN (“CN Infrastructure | Corpus Nummorum,” n.d.). The indicators are thus mentioned below via their identifiers after FAIRplus (“Level 4,” n.d.).

The publication in accordance with the FAIR principles enables the research data to be updated. The existence of the specialized portal CN facilitates the transformation of coin data and ensures long-term archiving and the necessary storage capacity. As the portal was developed for numismatic material from the same geographical area as Apollonia, its data model is compatible with the documentation of the collected data. (“CN data model | Corpus Nummorum,” n.d.). A new semantic modeling strategy as with Cluster Community (CC) 1 of the NFDi4Objects is not necessary when recording the data in CN, as a data model (Identifier DSM-4-C1) according to the numismatic specifications already exists (Peter et al., 2024).

By importing the data into this database, it automatically ensures compliance with the FAIR guidelines such as URIs (Principle F1), rich metadata through the specified fields (Principle F3), which are searchable (Identifier DSM-4-H2, DSM-4-H3, and Principle F4), IDs also for the metadata (Principle A1), access to the metadata through the LOD (Principle A2). They use restful JSON-API (Identifier DSM-4-R4 and Principle I1) as well as the ontology of nomisma.org and other thesauri (Identifier DSM-4-C4) (as in CC3 of NFDI4Objects) as metadata reference (Principle I2). Those are linked through it and within the database (Identifier DSM-4-C5 and Principle I3). The copyright CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0 (Identifier DSM-4-R6 and Principle R1) applies (“FAIR Principles,” n.d.).

Nevertheless, it is possible to consider the copyright restrictions imposed by the object owners and, for example, block images or other sensitive data to comply with all legal aspects of the publication. This means that this metadata does not have to be removed. If the data is to be released in the future, it can be unlocked, which gives flexibility in the selection of information to be published as OD. The retention of this data is of utmost importance for machine learning, especially in IR for coin dies or NLP (Gampe and Tolle, 2024). At the same time, they can be of essential scientific importance for overarching research topics or provenance research. This distinguishes the FAIRified from the printed publication, in which hidden metadata is not possible. In addition, not all images can be used as they exceed the printing costs. Due to the last two restrictions, too much data is lost. Finally, the linking of data through the node of a coin for objects with different backgrounds or metadata and the possibility of developing new questions based on them is only possible in the environment of the FAIR principles (Grozdanova, forthcoming).

The FAIRified Import: Step by Step

The data on the coins is available in two states: as an XLSX file with the data that was known before the complete analysis, and as catalog text, where the current version of the data records can be extracted. The data structure of CN was adhered to when creating the XLSX files. It should therefore be possible to extract the CSV files (Identifier DSM-4-R5) (as in CC2) without major changes to the content. However, no tables describe the metadata of some of the results of the study – that is the types and dies.

In the initial proposal, two procedures were implied. The first would include almost completely automated import and cleanup. The XLSX file would be tidied, and updated according to the catalog, and the fields adjusted according to the CN data model. Wherever necessary, ID codes would replace the data in the table. To do this, the entries of the missing metadata must be created in advance (e.g. missing owners, find spots, etc.). A major problem was the existence of entries on coins in CN that can lead to duplicate entries.

The second option would be the manual recording using the copy tool of CN for similar dies and types. Here the missing metadata can be added as required. This allows greater control

and immediate processing. In this case, coins that are already available in CN can be processed chronologically and assigned correctly. However, this would require more time depending on the errors made during an import. Through the discussions with the CN team, it became clear that a combined method is needed.

The very first step would be to create manually the missing standardized datasets (Identifier DSM-4-R2) both for CN and their partners (nomisma.org). These include for nomisma.org denominations (total 3), and persons (total 44) (Identifier DSM-4-C3). For CN those would be the standardized obverse legends (total 10), reverse legends (total 102), obverse descriptions (total 24), and reverse descriptions (total 55).

Following this step, the datasets for types and dies (Identifier DSM-4-R1) would be created as a table manually. Only the types will be imported manually through the mask of the CN editor, so duplicates can be avoided and already connected coins checked. The flat typology will be used and the “parenttype” tool will generate relations. The coin die table will be automatically imported. It contains only a few relevant parameters (as mentioned above) that will be harmonized: id, id_legend, id_design, name_die, side.

Then the type and die IDs can be manually added to the harmonized coin dataset (Identifier DSM-4-C2) after the established principles of CN (Identifier DSM-4-R3). Again, for the coins missing standardized datasets of owners or findspots will be created manually. After the discussion the fields of the coin table were specified and tidied so following groups emerged: coin_id, db coin_imagesets and coin_images, db coin_imagesets and coin_images, db coin_images object_type, db coin_images author, publication_state, id_die_o, id_die_r, coins_to_type, weight, diameter_min, diameter_max, axis, centerhole, id_owner, collection_id, id_owner_reproduction, plastercast_id, provenience, source_link, comment_private, comment_public_en, zotero_id, page, number, plate, picture, annotation.

Then the image datasets will be renamed after the numbers of the coins from the catalog. Afterwards, both images and the table can be automatically imported by the team of CN and then the data where a publication permit exists can be published online. It is to be noted that publications missing in Zotero must be added manually too in order to achieve a flawless import of the coin data set.

The Scholarly Gain

This dataship helps export and publish in a controlled environment a die study so it would be adjustable, reusable, and accessible for all future research. The imports were optimized in accordance with world standards ensured by CN.

This data is important not only for the future of research in the region of Apollonia, but also for numismatics in general for it contains types, descriptions, and other collected information used in cross-studies (Ivanova-Anaplioti, forthcoming). That will be profitable for large-scale

projects not only as CN but also ARCH, RPC, and others (“ARCH,” n.d.; “IRIS,” n.d.; “RPC online,” n.d.).

The mentioned cross-studies are yet to develop on a large scale. Interlinking on a cultural level through common characteristics is destined to be fragmented when relevant publications are still not searchable. Big datasets must be accessible so that material and monument groups can find the common parameters for evaluation. Only then will we be able to answer research questions that have been lingering because of the lack of manpower to manage the data. Digital numismatic datasets will allow us to accelerate the process of finding the cross-points. They are the parameter hub in many of the characteristics of other materials and have an advantage in digital tools. This will help polish the methodology of this future scholarly procedure.

One additional argument for the urgency of the FAIRification of this data is the robberies of museums and the forgeries. Coins are an easy target for both. This dataship would invest not only in the accessibility of provenance but also in preventing criminal activities, protecting the collections in museums, and in such a way our heritage.

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